

Youth, Culture & Sports

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Youth, Culture & Sports, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Youth with above basic overall digital skills” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data for Kosovo* not available. Data for North Macedonia for 2023 not available.

Source
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/isoc_sk_dskl_i21__custom_14882522/default/table?lang=en&page=time:2023 (accessed 13 February 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Ministerial Meeting on Culture

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives		Cultural cooperation fostered	Regional cooperation and people-to-people exchanges	
	Mobility and cooperation initiatives	Support to implementation of the EU acquis	Participation in the Culture Moves Europe initiative	Participation in SHARE 2.0 initiative	European Week of Sport
Albania	Increased number of Erasmus+ (E+) projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the POLICY ANSWERS (PA) Western Balkans Mobility Scheme (WBMS)	No twinning projects or TAIEX missions	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility One selected residency host	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised Number of participants and partnering organisations not specified
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the PA WBMS	No twinning projects implemented No new TAIEX missions reported	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility One selected residency host	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Kosovo	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the PA WBMS	Increased number of twinning projects and TAIEX missions reported	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility One selected residency host	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Montenegro	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the PA WBMS	No twinning projects or TAIEX missions	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility No residency host reported	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised Number of participants and partnering organisations decreasing
North Macedonia	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the PA WBMS	No twinning projects implemented Increased number of TAIEX missions reported	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility One selected residency host	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Serbia	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented Participation in the PA WBMS	Increased number of twinning projects and TAIEX missions reported	Increased number of beneficiaries for individual mobility One selected residency host	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation

Legend: Information not available

Highlights

Great success of the Western Balkans partners in the Culture Moves Europe initiative
Increased participation in the European Heritage Hub by including the Western Balkans economies in the Policy Monitor
Montenegro hosting the 3rd European Heritage Hub Forum "EU Enlargement: Cultural Heritage as a Key Resource for Cities & Civil Society" (3-4 April 2025)

